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SRNHS Celebrates 47th Foundation Anniversary

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Sto. Rosario National High School, San Juan, La Union, celebrated its 47th Foundation Anniversary with the theme “SRNHS at 47: Crossing Bridges for Quality Education and Excellent Service” on March 13–14, 2024, headed by Dr. Maribel C. Reyes, Principal IV. Days to pay tribute, honor, and celebrate what has been accomplished over the last 47 years, as well as to look forward to what is yet to come.

The celebration started with a Holy Mass on March 13, 2024, by the officiating priest, Rev. Fr. Jan Eroll Mante. On March 14, 2024, the school conducted Zumba, Breakfast Salo-Salo, and dance competitions showcasing the vibrant talents of each grade level: Modern Folk, Zumba, Ballroom, Hip-Hop, Retro, and Festival Dance.

For Grade 8 Level, considering the efforts and dedications, the Grade 8-STE wrapped up the celebration with these awards of recognition: Dance Competition—Champion: Zumba Dance & Most Entertaining Group, and other school contests: 1st Place: Best Waste Management Implementer, 1st Place: Best Maintained Classroom, 1st Place: Cleanest Zone, and 3rd Place: Best Gulayan Implementer.

Indeed, this is a day to celebrate the history, revisit, and reconnect with the continuing journey of the school. That is why Foundation Day is so important—it is a celebration of excellence that makes SRNHS one!

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